

LLMs for Software Development- Interview Questionnaire

1. What is your role at your organisation?
2. Which LLM-based tools do you use for your work-related tasks?
3. What use case(s) did you use LLMs for? (e.g., requirements engineering, design, coding, testing, deployment, documentation, maintenance, etc.)
4. What was your primary motivation/intention for using LLMs for your use case(s)? (e.g., automate parts or whole tasks, learn new things, etc.)
5. How did the integration of LLMs change your workflows? Can you share specific examples?
6. What are the main benefits you have experienced using LLMs?
7. What challenges or limitations have you encountered while using LLMs?
8. Have you discovered any strategies to maximise the benefits while minimising the limitations and challenges of using LLMs? (trade-off mechanisms, evaluation techniques or metrics, etc.)
9. What best practices would you recommend for using LLMs in software development? (e.g., LLM integration approaches, human oversight mechanisms, skills required)
10. Is there anything else you'd like to share about your experience using LLMs in software development?